

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B400
 Date: 18/09/08
 Take Off: 07:46:16Z
 Landing: 12:15:11Z
 Flight Time 4h 28m 55s

Campaign: CAVIAR

Operating Area: Camborne

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Clare Lee	Met Office	Y
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	Y
6	Core Chem / AVAPS / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	N/Y
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	Met Office	
8	ARIES	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	N
9	CVI	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	N
10	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	Y
11	AMS	Gavin McMeeking	University of Manchester	N
12	TAFTS	Ralph Beeby	Imperial College	N
13	Wet & Dry Neph / PSAP	Simon Osborne	Met Office	N/Y
14	MARSS / DEIMOS	Dave Pollard	Met Office	Y
15				
16				
17				
18				

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B400
 Date: 18 Sept 2008
 Project: CAVIAR
 Location: Camborne

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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080625		Start-Up	0.00 kft	356	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
074616		T/O	0.65 kft	030	Cranfield
080210		Video	14.1 kft	254	Start FFC,RFC,UFC,DFC
082725	083451	Run 1	20.0 kft	209	A-B
082740		Sonde	20.0 kft	195	Launch #01
083101		Ovhd	20.0 kft	195	Camborne
083245		Sonde	20.0 kft	192	Launch #02
083510	085055	Profile 1	19.3 - 5.5 kft	193	1kfp
085055	090437	Run 2	5.5 kft	036	1kfp B-A
085900		Ovhd	5.5 kft	017	Camborne
090437	091147	Profile 2	5.5 - -.21 kft	017	To 50',Q1023
091147	091448	Run 3	-.21 - -.11 kft	198	100',Q1023
091205		Heimann	-.16 kft	197	Cal
091448	091602	Profile 3	-.11 - 1.4 kft	198	100-1700'
091603	091843	Run 3	1.5 - 1.4 kft	193	1700'
091843	092048	Profile 4	1.4 - -.11 kft	188	1700'-100'
092048	092251	Run 3	-.11 kft	196	100'
093423	093852	Profile 5	2.2 - 6.1 kft	291	Track Cmbn sonde
093859	101436	Profile 5	6.2 - 33.0 kft	243	Interrupt for ATC
101232		JW & Nevz	32.7 kft	201	Zero
101844	102552	Profile 5	33.0 - 34.0 kft	042	
102553	103252	Run 4	34.0 kft	177	
102604		Sonde	34.0 kft	177	Launch #03
102801		Sonde	34.0 kft	196	Launch #04
103253	103821	Profile 6	34.0 - 29.0 kft	192	B
103821	105126	Run 5	29.1 - 29.0 kft	079	B-A
104230		Sonde	29.0 kft	030	Launch #05
104754		Sonde	29.0 kft	021	Launch #06
105126	110634	Profile 7	29.0 - 14.6 kft	018	At A
110302		Event	18.2 kft	348	Intermittent contrails
110634	111504	Run 6	14.6 - 14.5 kft	192	A-B
111038		Ovhd	14.5 kft	193	Camborne
111505	112419	Profile 8	14.5 - 5.0 kft	190	At B
112419	112937	Run 7	5.0 kft	013	B-Camborne
112937	113749	Profile 9	5.0 - -.25 kft	018	Cambne, to 50'
113759	113959	Run 8	-.17 - -.16 kft	194	100'
113832		Heimann	-.18 kft	193	Cal
114012	114134	Profile 10	0.07 - 1.4 kft	197	100-1.7k'
114134	114344	Run 8	1.4 kft	194	100, Q1023-B
114345	114554	Profile 11	1.4 - -.13 kft	194	1.7k'-100',Q1023
114555	114753	Run 8	-.13 - -.17 kft	193	100'
121511		Land	-.18 kft	079	Exeter
121732		ASP	-.17 kft	066	Closed
122101		Shutdown	-.19 kft	263	50'44.15N, 3'25.11W

B400 Track 18-SEP-08

7°W 6°W 5°W 4°W 3°W 2°W 1°W 0°

CAVIAR water vapour continuum flight B400
18 September 2008

Take off Cranfield: 0830L (0730Z)

Land Exeter: 1300L (1200Z)

Location: Cornish peninsula in vicinity of Camborne radiosonde station. Straight and level runs should be conducted partially over sea and partially over land, intercepting the location of the ground station during the run.

Weather conditions: Clear sky (or very nearly clear sky) from surface to space

Important instruments: ARIES, TAFTS, SWS, MARSS, DEIMOS, AVAPS, all water vapour instruments, core chemistry, PCASP

Sortie aim: to sample intensively the water vapour structure of the atmosphere in the area around Camborne, and measure the radiative signature of the water vapour continuum. Also to intercompare sonde and aircraft instruments.

Coordinates: aim to fly straight and level runs between coordinates

A = 50.08°N, 4.51°W (Southeast point)

B = °N, °W (Northwest point, variable with TAS)

The runs are nominally of 10 mins duration, but in practice these will be of longer (shorter) duration at minimum (maximum) altitude.

Radiometers: ARIES, TAFTS and SWS to measure a mix of upwelling and downwelling radiances; ARIES to use NadZen30secLongRun script.

Note that the exact selection of flight altitudes will be made by the mission scientist, depending on the humidity structure of the atmosphere for each flight. In general, it is most useful to concentrate flight levels where the humidity is highest.

Camborne radiosonde ascents: an extra balloon launch has been requested for **0940Z**. Communications between the aircraft and the ground will be made via satellite phone.

Sortie items – flight levels are examples only

1. Take off from Cranfield **0730Z** and transit to area of operations around Camborne. Arrive at intermediate altitude conducive to fuel economy, e.g. FL200. (45 min)
2. Perform straight and level run (SLR) at FL200 between A and B, dropping two sondes (10 mins, 57 total)
3. Descend in the turn to FL120, rate of descent 1000 ft/min (10 mins, 67 total)
4. Perform SLR (B to A) at FL120 (10 mins, 77 total)
5. Descend in the turn to FL060, rate of descent 1000 ft/min (10 mins, 87 total)
6. Perform SLR (A to B) at FL060 (10 mins, 97 total)
7. Step profile from B down to 50 feet over ocean, finishing near B, rate of descent as decided by mission scientist (12 mins, 109 total)
8. Perform SLR (B to A) at 100 feet, ascending at 1000 ft/min on approach to coast to reach minimum safety altitude (MSA) and continuing run at MSA for rest of run. It is important to allow at least 3-4 minutes at 100 feet for ARIES and Heimann (10 mins, 119 total)
9. Aircraft to position for sonde launch at MSA (10 mins, 129 total)
10. **Camborne sonde launch requested for 0940Z.** Aircraft to perform a spiral or polygon ascent to “chase” the sonde, keeping in visual contact as long as possible. Ascend to maximum altitude FL350 (35 mins, 164 total)
11. Reposition aircraft for straight and level run (10 mins, 174 total)
12. Perform SLR between A and B (either A to B, or B to A) at FL350, dropping two sondes (10 mins, 184 total). Ideally to coincide with **MetOp satellite overpass at 1028Z.**
13. Descend in the turn to FL230, rate of descent 1000 ft/min (14 mins, 198 total)
14. Perform SLR between A and B at FL230, dropping two sondes (10 mins, 208 total)
15. Descend in the turn to FL120, rate of descent 1000 ft/min (15 mins, 223 total)
16. Perform SLR between A and B at FL120 (10 mins, 233 total)
17. Descend in the turn to FL060, rate of descent 1000 ft/min (8 mins, 241 total)
18. Perform SLR between A and B at FL060 (10 mins, 251 total)
19. Descend in the turn to MSA, rate of descent as decided by mission scientist (5 mins, 256 total)
20. Perform SLR between A and B at MSA (10 mins, 266 total)
21. Reposition aircraft for landing at Exeter (10 mins, 276 total)
22. Refuel prior to second (aerosol) sortie.

NB Special request from Camborne staff: aerial photos over Camborne site!

Mission Scientist Debrief

CAVIAR

B400

18th September 2008

Clare Lee

Weather conditions:

Completely clear skies in operational area. Quite hazy at low levels with high aerosol loading measured. Towards the end of the flight Cu started to build over land, but didn't affect the immediate operating area.

Operating area:

SW approaches, between fixed ground points: Northerly point A (50°32'N 5°10'W) and Southerly point B (49°53'N 5°27'W). This track overpasses Camborne ground facility (50.217N, 5.317W) with nearly equidistant stretches of sea either side. The MetOp suborbital track was also close to the area at ~1028. Take off was from Cranfield with a refuel at Exeter.

Sortie:

Initially there was a delayed take-off due to air-traffic. This meant the manoeuvres before the overpass had to be shortened to be at max altitude during the satellite overpass, and it shortened the total sortie length to be below the crew duty time due to the following ADIENT flight.

A run at FL200 was made, with 2 dropsondes launched to characterise the humidity profile below. A moist layer was identified at ~5500ft. A profile descent to FL055 was made, showing variable humidity at several layers. A run at FL055 was flown in that moist layer. A descent profile was made to 100ft to characterise the rest of the atmosphere, where layers of aerosol were measured. This was followed by a run at 100ft to characterise the sea surface temperature. The sea was calm with gentle waves. The run was interrupted to ascend over the land, and Camborne, at 1700ft and descended back down to 100ft the other side. The aircraft returned to Camborne to perform a balloon sonde chasing manoeuvre starting at 2000ft. Launch of the sonde occurred at 0932. The aircraft performed a very tight left hand bank to maintain the balloon in sight. Due to the high banking the aircraft could not ascend as quickly as the sonde and hence the aircraft levelled out to have a faster climb rate. Turns were made to keep within the launch area. At ~23kft the balloon was observed out of the window and hence was also not drifting far from the area. The ascent was interrupted at FL330 due to air-traffic. Ascent to FL350 was then attempted but could not be achieved with the aircraft performance. A run at FL340 was performed with 2 dropsondes launched fractionally before the satellite overpass, and staggered to measure different altitudes during the overpass. A descent to FL290, a moist layer, was made followed by a run at FL290. 2 more sondes were launched. A descent to FL145, another moister layer, was made followed by a run. This was repeated but down at FL050. A profile descent was made down to 50ft, followed by a run at 100ft above the sea and interrupted at 1700ft over land. At the end of the run was the end of the science due to time constraints, however all instruments continued to make measurements in the transit back to Exeter at FL050.

Instruments:

Wetneph was operated as required for 2nd flight of the day (ADIENT). Useful as high aerosol loading was encountered below 6000ft.

ARIES: At the beginning of the science ARIES was seeing low values and hence rebooted. After reboot better raw values were seen, but the BT display was showing unrealistic values.

TAFTS: Worked through the whole flight.

Mission Scientist's Log

CLARE LEE

Flight No **B.400**.....

Date **18/9/08**.....

Page **1** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
074650					Take off delayed due to other aircraft coming in and ATC holdings
		FL200	225		Transit. to pt. A (Mully part)
					T = -18.73°C, T _D = -43.54°C
					wind 17ms ⁻¹ 140°
					aircraft wind 039/134
082725	RI	FL200	195	50°26'N 50°12'W	run at A.
082740	DI				drop sonde 1.
					winds 18ms ⁻¹ 141°
083016					ARRIS issue - not seeing much recharging. - had been OK.
					Weather - clear sky in immediate area
					to further to South (not in recovery area). Quite hazy.
083245	DS2				Drop sonde 2.
					determined wet layer ~ 5500ft.
083450			192	49°48'N 50°26'W	At point B.
083451	RI				End run 1
083451	PI ↓				slow turn in descent to retain sonde information
084137					Drop sonde 2 landed.
0847					ARRIS working again, but unsure if full OK.
					Going to do a cal in profile so can do BT on screen plot, to see if reasonable #'s.

7846L

Mission Scientist's Log

CLARE LEE

Flight No **B400**.....

Date **18/9/08**.....

Page **2** of **5**...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
085055	P1end				
085055	R2	FLOSS	016		Start on B → A. winds $7ms^{-1} 158^\circ$ aircraft wind: $066/14$ knots $T = 1.13^\circ C$ $T_D = -0.85^\circ C$ Structure in moisture between FL200 + FLOSS ~ 100ft. → 70ft, 5.50ft.
085913					MAOSS seeing slightly moister over Camborne than at pt B (~50ft in some channels) above aircraft. Cloud physics: seeing aged aerosol type particles
090437	R2end	FLOSS			end run at A.
090437	R2	FLOSS			descending profile turning to right PLASP seeing layers in aerosol structure in descent, wetup seeing high concs. aerosol. Descent all around pt. A area (North pt.)
090437 091152	P2end	100ft.			Sea - gentle waves
091152 091152	R3	100ft.	197	50°24'N 5017'W	over sea.
0915	P3				ascending due to the aircraft + land.
091603	R3	1700ft.	193	50°21'N 5018'W	run continuing over land.

Mission Scientist's Log

CLARE LEE

Flight No **B**.....400.....

Date ..18/19/08.....

Page 3 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
091843	P4 ↓	1700ft.			people back down to sea level. aerial: repeating 100ft → 6000ft. high arcs.
092048	R3	100ft.			recommencing low level over sea.
092251	R3end				ARRIES did all nadir with cats in profiles, during 100ft run.
0924		2000ft.	013		Running at 2000ft back to Camborne. Sonde launch time 093200
093423	P5				At Camborne chasing sonde. very tight left bank to keep with sonde
0938		5500ft.			Sonde ascending faster than we can whilst turning - leveling at + ascending but keeping in general area. Weather: occasional low over land in distance
0954		~236ft.			Saw balloon out right hand window
1000					Weather still clear in operation area cloud building from N + NE SFC + G
101836	P1end	FL330			Interrupt of profile due to air traffic
101844	P5rec	FL330			recommence profile upto FL350 difficulty in getting to FL350
102553	P5end				rene day next run at FL340

Mission Scientist's Log

CLARE LEE

Flight No **B**.....400.....

Date ..18/9/08.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
102553	R4	FL340	180		Run A → B (max alt.)
102604	DS3				Sonde dropped at A
102801	DS4				Sonde dropped slightly north of Camborne
					no GPS data during another one
					GPS came back
					low str ⁸¹⁸ just past point B (to South)
103253	R6 and P6 ↓	FL340			
103821	P6 and R5	FL290			Extended run from South of B
104230	D55	FL290	028		Sonde dropped at pt. R. T = -37.52°C, T _D = -40.18°C wind = 29ms ⁻¹ / 32° aircraft wind 042° / 65 knts
104710					Over Lead Camborne
104754	DS6	FL290	021		Sonde dropped over coast
105126	R5 and	FL290			end run at point A
105126	P7 ↓				Descending in turn
110634	P7 and	FL145			level for most layer
110634	R6	FL145	193		A → B
111039					Over Camborne
					Small w puffs just to right - lining up with coast
111505	R6 and	FL145			At B
111505	P8 ↓				descending

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.400**.....

 Date **18/9/08**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1122					Waxfler: generally clear. Line small in lining up along coast (North)
112419	P8end	5000ft.	016		MEB leading N.
112419	R7	FL50			Due to time constraints going to do 1/2 run only
112937	R7end	FL50			end run
112937	P9↓	FL50	018		profiling down to 100ft post Camborne.
					Cloud physics reporting noise on PLASP + FTSSP.
113458				50°30' N 5°12' W	turning around
					Also point where ^{sea} turns much darker (deeper?)
113749	P9end	50ft.			Run started slightly South of pt. A (descending still prior)
113759	R8	100ft.			
113959	R8 P10				Interrupted due to land ascent to 1700ft.
114134	R8	1700ft.			some turbulence.
114345	R8int.	1700ft.			
114345	P11↓	1700ft.			descending back over sea South side.
114555	A1end	100ft			
114555	R8inc.	100ft.			recommencing run.
114753	R8end			49°24' N 5°26' W	End science
		5000ft			Still take data through.

 ~1300Z
(1300L)

 Land Enter.
 (w ~ 5000ft - went through it on transit.)

Flight:

B400

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B400

Date: 17/09/08

Instruments

1. TWC – Preflight Source Current jumping between 1014 and 999 DRSU, Status bit at 4088. Switch off / on
2. CVI – Preflight problem with pc, rebooted then okay.
3. Mission Scientist laptop – problems with mouse out of control on switch on. Rebooted then okay.
4. CPC – Error Message after T/O from AIM software “The parameter is incorrect”
5. 2DP – lots of noise after take-off
6. ARIES – okay initially but started going wrong on transit to Camborne. Switch off/ on. Looking a bit better (0845Z). Brightness temperatures rubbish. Improved on 2nd half of flight
7. AVAPS – Sonde #04, no GPS data initially, then mainly okay. Some data gaps though.
8. Temperature logger – setup “AVAPS” sensor at FM pc. Moved to AVAPS rack approx 0945Z.
9. Cloud physics – FFSSP bit noisy, PCASP noisy towards end. CIP & PIP duff data
- 10.

FWVS - okay

Neph – no comms to chiller otherwise okay

PSAP - okay

TAFTS –it worked perfectly! Still problem with laser though.

SWS – Lower shims module not working (ongoing issue)

SHIMS - okay

AMS – pumping down only, no data.

Core Chem - okay

MARSS - okay

DEIMOS – data suspect

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

Nil

MPDS

Check for B402 sortie brief - CAVIAR

Satcom-H Calls

2 x CAVIAR (to Camborne)

Issues

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 12/9/8

Flight No: B 400
M2.3?

Pre-Flighter: C. Cotton

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	NR
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☐	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	NR

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	} left to operator
26	☐	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	☐	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	☐	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	Not filled
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☒	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41	☒	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☒	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		<u>Signed</u>
45	☐	ICEX applied		
46	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
47	☐	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

B400CVI.txt

9/18/08 7:55:59 AM Re-started after take-off as getting no PCASP data. After dodgy
period now appears ok - no explanation
9/18/08 8:27:49 AM Start of run 1.
9/18/08 8:32:57 AM Dropsonde 2
9/18/08 8:35:37 AM Start of profile 1
9/18/08 8:51:40 AM start of run 2 slr fl055
9/18/08 9:04:49 AM end of run
9/18/08 9:05:10 AM start of porofile 2 descent to 50ft
9/18/08 9:12:15 AM end of descent start of slr at fl001
9/18/08 9:15:13 AM start of climb
9/18/08 9:16:33 AM slr at fl017 over land
9/18/08 9:19:05 AM descent to fl001
9/18/08 9:21:07 AM start of slr at fl001 (continuation of run 3)
9/18/08 9:23:11 AM end of run
9/18/08 12:25:20 PM

ARIES flight log

Flight: B400 page 1 of 2

Date: 18/09/08 Operator(s): D. TIDEMAN Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CAUIAR Cambridge

Scans: either "[IGMs][co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Comments
		30s	CH				} NZ (carrier)
		30s	N				
		30s	CH				
		30s	Z				
		1min	CH				} N3 (SST)
		3min	N				
075700	Transit	1x60	CBB	0			Mirror check script
		1x60	HBB	0			(error found 200ms instead of 2000)
081625	Transit	1x60	CBB	C	7083	3091	} CH script
	FL200	1x60	HBB	C	7083	3061	
082726	FL200	NZ NZ		0	7072	3066	Dropsonde run
							Aries went a bit strange shutdown + started again
084730	Profile	CH cal		C	708	3027	
085130	Run 2	NZ		0	708	3059	} Accident checked note base script
	FLOSS						
085418	Run 2	NZ		0	7067	3044	Stopped and started script
	FLOSS						
085550	Run 2	NZ		0	7051	3044	Stopped + started again!
	FLOSS						
090437	Run 2	NZ		0	7056	3049	Stopped script (end of run)
091152	Run 3	N3		0	7076	3031	
	100ft						
091524							Clins started after
091533		Z 30s					Zenith view over land

allly
start/stops
with bugs

B400_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

05:51:47.87 --- - - - -
05:51:47.87 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
05:51:47.87 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
05:51:47.87 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B400
05:51:47.87 --- - - - -
05:52:13.06 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
05:52:20.09 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
05:52:28.10 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
05:52:29.21 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
05:52:30.21 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
05:52:35.80 SWS - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
05:52:40.10 SWS - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 1000ms.
05:52:44.86 USH - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 1000ms.
05:52:46.71 USH - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
05:52:49.00 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:52:50.78 USH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
05:52:50.78 USH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
05:52:53.78 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:52:55.51 LSH - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 1000ms.
05:52:56.76 LSH - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
05:52:59.27 LSH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
05:52:59.27 LSH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
05:53:01.26 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:53:04.19 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
05:53:08.05 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
05:53:20.41 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:53:20.42 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:53:20.42 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:53:21.91 SWS - - - - Idling
05:53:22.38 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
05:53:30.05 SWS - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
05:53:30.05 SWS - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
05:53:31.60 LSH - - - - Idling
05:53:31.85 USH - - - - Idling
05:53:32.55 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:53:34.80 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:53:34.81 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:53:36.24 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
05:53:43.47 SWS - - - - Idling
05:53:45.26 USH - - - - Idling
05:53:45.46 LSH - - - - Idling
05:53:47.37 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
05:53:47.38 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
05:53:47.39 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:11:03.40 SWS - - - - Idling
07:11:03.96 LSH - - - - Idling
07:11:03.99 USH - - - - Idling
07:11:08.15 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
07:11:26.68 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:11:26.69 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:11:26.70 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:11:28.31 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:11:37.56 LSH - - - - Idling
07:11:37.59 USH - - - - Idling
07:11:37.86 SWS - - - - Idling
07:18:17.14 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:18:17.15 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:18:17.16 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:18:18.77 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:18:28.04 LSH - - - - Idling
07:18:28.04 USH - - - - Idling
07:18:28.14 SWS - - - - Idling
07:18:48.25 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:18:48.26 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:18:48.27 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:21:01.59 --- - - - - *** Freezer temp 10 deg C

```

07:21:17.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:21:18.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:21:18.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:23:43.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:23:43.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:23:43.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:23:44.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:23:54.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:23:54.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:23:54.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:24:02.58	USH	-	-	-	1000	NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 1000ms.
07:24:11.70	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
07:24:15.07	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
07:24:17.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:24:19.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:24:25.43	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 300ms.
07:24:25.43	LSH	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 300ms.
07:24:27.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:24:28.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:24:31.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:24:35.21	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 300ms.
07:24:35.23	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 300ms.
07:24:39.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:24:43.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:24:48.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:24:48.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:24:48.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:28:40.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:41.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:41.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:41.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:28:42.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:28:44.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:28:44.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:28:49.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:28:52.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:28:52.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:28:53.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:28:55.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:28:57.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:47:42.88	SWS	89.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:47:44.02	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:47:46.05	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:47:53.47	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
07:47:53.47	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
07:47:58.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:48:03.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:48:03.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:48:05.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:48:05.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:48:05.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:48:05.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:48:06.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:48:06.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:48:08.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:48:11.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:48:11.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:48:11.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:51:22.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:51:25.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:51:46.29	LSH	-	-	1000	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 1000ms.
07:51:46.30	LSH	-	-	-	1000	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 1000ms.
07:51:49.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:51:50.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:52:00.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:52:02.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:52:03.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:52:06.29	SWS	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
07:52:06.29	SWS	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.

07:52:09.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:52:13.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:52:16.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:52:17.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:52:25.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:52:27.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:52:30.33	USH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
07:52:30.33	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
07:52:31.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:52:36.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:52:37.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:52:41.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:52:44.45	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
07:52:44.46	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
07:52:48.94	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 200ms.
07:52:51.37	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
07:52:53.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:52:58.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:52:59.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:58:53.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:58:54.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:58:59.61	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:59:00.03	SWS	-4.1	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
07:59:03.75	SWS	39.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:59:04.22	SWS	39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
07:59:06.25	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:59:11.21	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:59:17.84	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
07:59:19.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:59:25.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:59:29.34	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
07:59:29.34	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
07:59:31.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:59:32.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:59:40.98	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:59:41.40	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
07:59:45.94	SWS	39.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:59:46.61	SWS	31.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:59:47.33	SWS	23.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:59:48.05	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:59:48.77	SWS	5.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:59:49.81	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:59:54.07	SWS	-5.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:59:55.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:00:00.24	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:00.66	SWS	-4.1	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
08:00:05.17	SWS	39.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:00:05.84	SWS	31.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:00:06.58	SWS	23.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:00:07.30	SWS	14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:00:08.02	SWS	5.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:00:08.75	SWS	-2.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:09.48	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:10.20	SWS	-20.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:10.92	SWS	-28.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:11.65	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:12.37	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:20.38	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:00:28.41	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:36.42	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:00:44.45	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:52.42	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:01:00.46	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:01:01.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** Contrails
08:01:08.48	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:01:09.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:01:10.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:01:14.01	SWS	-17.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:01:15.46	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000

08:01:19.44	SWS	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.
08:01:22.42	SWS	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
08:01:22.44	SWS	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
08:01:24.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:01:31.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:01:40.03	SWS	-	333	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 333ms.
08:01:42.09	SWS	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 333ms to 1000ms.
08:01:45.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:01:46.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:01:55.49	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:02:03.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:02:03.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:02:03.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:02:04.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:02:07.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:02:09.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:02:12.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:02:12.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:02:13.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:02:16.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:09:57.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 8 deg C
08:12:38.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:12:39.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:12:39.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:12:43.06	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:12:47.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:12:47.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:12:47.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:12:48.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:12:51.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:12:53.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:12:54.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:12:54.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:12:57.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:12:58.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:13:01.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:13:04.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:13:04.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:13:04.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:23:44.07	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
08:23:46.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:23:47.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:23:48.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:23:54.59	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
08:23:54.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:23:58.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:23:59.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:24:00.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:04.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:24:05.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:24:07.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:24:18.57	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
08:24:18.59	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
08:24:22.16	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
08:24:23.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:25.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:24:32.79	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
08:24:32.80	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
08:24:34.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:37.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:24:40.61	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:24:47.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:47.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:47.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:48.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:24:49.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:24:50.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:24:53.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:53.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

08:24:57.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:24:58.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:24:58.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:25:05.17	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:25:07.24	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:25:10.02	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:25:13.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:26:26.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:27:14.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:27:14.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:27:15.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:27:27.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:27:27.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:27:27.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:29:03.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:29:04.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:29:06.73	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
08:29:08.44	SWS	179.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:29:09.38	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
08:29:11.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:30:47.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:30:47.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:30:54.25	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:30:55.97	SWS	0.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:30:57.59	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:30:59.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:32:33.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:32:34.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:32:39.76	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
08:32:41.48	SWS	179.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:32:42.45	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
08:32:44.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:34:18.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:34:19.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:34:22.51	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:34:24.23	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:34:25.13	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:34:27.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:35:19.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:35:19.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:35:19.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:35:33.00	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:35:38.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:35:38.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:35:38.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:35:39.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:35:40.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:35:41.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:35:49.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:36:23.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:36:23.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:36:23.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:36:24.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:36:25.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:36:26.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:36:33.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:36:35.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:36:35.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:36:35.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:42:36.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:42:41.48	SWS	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.
08:42:44.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:42:47.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:42:49.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:42:52.59	USH	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.
08:42:55.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:42:59.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:42:59.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:42:59.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

08:43:02.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:02.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:02.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:03.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:43:04.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:43:04.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:43:12.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:43:13.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:43:13.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:43:13.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:47:34.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:47:35.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:47:40.58	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
08:47:42.30	SWS	179.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:47:43.29	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
08:47:45.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:29.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:49:29.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:49:29.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:49:32.47	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:49:39.64	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:49:49.19	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
08:49:52.71	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
08:49:56.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:56.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:56.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:57.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:49:58.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:49:59.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:50:07.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:50:11.76	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
08:50:37.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:50:37.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:50:37.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:50:38.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:50:39.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:50:39.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:50:47.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:50:55.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:50:55.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:50:55.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:27.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:52:28.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:52:30.68	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:52:32.41	SWS	0.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:52:33.35	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:52:35.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:54:06.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:54:10.81	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
08:54:12.50	SWS	179.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:54:13.59	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
08:54:15.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:54:23.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:54:24.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:54:25.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:57:02.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:57:03.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:05.32	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:57:07.05	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:57:08.02	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:57:09.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:57:54.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:57:55.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:58:01.66	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
08:58:03.39	SWS	179.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:58:04.37	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
08:58:06.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:59:56.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:59:57.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

09:00:02.39	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:00:04.11	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:00:05.57	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:00:07.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:00:34.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
09:01:40.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:40.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:01:46.34	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:01:48.07	SWS	179.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:01:49.02	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:01:49.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:03:29.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:03:30.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:03:38.34	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:03:40.07	SWS	0.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:03:41.53	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:03:42.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:04:38.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:04:38.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:04:39.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:04:41.06	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:04:45.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:04:45.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:04:45.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:04:46.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:04:48.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:04:48.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:04:49.82	SWS	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.
09:04:52.25	USH	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.
09:04:54.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:04:54.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:04:55.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:04:56.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:04:56.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:04:57.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:05:01.77	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
09:05:01.78	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
09:05:08.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:05:13.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:06:25.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:25.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:25.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:08:16.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:08:23.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:08:27.45	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
09:08:27.46	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
09:08:29.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:08:31.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:08:35.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:08:45.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:08:45.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:08:45.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:08:46.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:08:46.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:08:46.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:08:48.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:08:49.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:08:49.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:08:57.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:08:57.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:08:57.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:08:57.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:08:59.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:08:59.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:00.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:09:00.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:09:02.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:03.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:08.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

09:09:09.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:09.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:09.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:53.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:53.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:54.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:58.55	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
09:10:01.96	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
09:10:05.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:05.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:05.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:06.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:10:07.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:07.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:09.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:09.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:11.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:12.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:15.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:15.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:15.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:34.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:34.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:36.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:37.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:46.33	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:10:48.06	SWS	179.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:10:48.96	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:10:50.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:49.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:11:49.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:11:49.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:11:56.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:56.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:56.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:12:38.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:12:39.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:12:41.79	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:12:43.52	SWS	0.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:12:44.42	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:12:45.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:13:40.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:13:40.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:13:43.26	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:13:44.99	SWS	179.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:13:45.93	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:13:47.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:15:49.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:15:51.06	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:15:52.78	SWS	0.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:15:54.25	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:15:55.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:16:34.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:16:35.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:16:36.73	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:16:38.47	SWS	179.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:16:39.38	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:16:40.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:35.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:18:36.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:41.06	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:18:42.82	SWS	0.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:18:43.90	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:18:45.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:19:54.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:19:55.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:19:57.04	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:19:57.37	SWS	15.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:19:59.11	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.

09:20:00.00	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:20:01.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:20:53.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
09:21:54.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:21:55.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:21:57.14	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:21:58.88	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:22:00.00	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:22:02.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:22:53.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:22:53.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:22:54.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:22:56.09	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:23:00.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:00.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:00.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:01.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:23:02.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:02.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:10.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:11.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:11.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:11.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:13.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:23:14.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:14.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:22.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:29.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:29.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:29.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:30.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:23:32.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:32.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:40.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:56.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:56.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:56.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:23:57.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:23:59.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:59.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:24:07.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:24:57.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:24:57.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:24:57.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:26:04.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:26:05.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:26:09.62	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:26:11.36	SWS	179.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:26:12.84	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
09:26:15.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:07.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:29:08.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:29:15.07	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:29:16.55	SWS	31.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:29:18.26	SWS	31.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:29:20.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:24.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:29:27.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:29:28.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:29:30.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:29:31.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:33.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:29:34.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:29:35.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:29:36.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:29:37.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:29:38.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:29:47.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:29:48.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

```

09:30:22.36 --- - - - - *** Freezer temp 10 deg C
09:31:19.98 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:31:20.21 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:31:29.71 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:31:30.64 SWS - - - - Idling
09:31:33.14 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
09:31:33.15 SWS - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
09:31:34.95 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:31:36.40 SWS - - - - Idling
09:31:37.01 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:31:40.35 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:31:41.28 USH - - - - Idling
09:31:43.32 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:31:43.34 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:31:44.05 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:31:46.00 USH - - - - Idling
09:31:46.42 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:34:30.39 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:35:29.80 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:36:30.71 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:37:31.08 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:38:44.79 USH - - - - Idling
09:38:44.84 SWS - - - - Idling
09:38:44.87 LSH - - - - Idling
09:38:53.27 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:38:53.28 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:38:53.29 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:38:54.43 SWS - - - - Idling
09:38:54.73 USH - - - - Idling
09:38:54.92 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:38:55.55 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:38:55.56 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:39:04.14 LSH - - - - Idling
09:39:04.56 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:48:35.60 USH - - - - Idling
09:48:35.69 SWS - - - - Idling
09:48:36.44 LSH - - - - Idling
09:48:37.59 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:48:42.85 SWS - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.
09:48:44.82 USH - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.
09:48:50.96 SWS - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 400ms.
09:48:50.97 SWS - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 400ms.
09:48:55.02 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
09:48:55.03 USH - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
09:48:56.97 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:48:56.98 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:48:56.99 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:48:58.21 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:49:00.37 USH - - - - Idling
09:49:01.51 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:49:02.59 SWS - - - - Idling
09:49:03.01 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:49:03.98 USH - - - - Idling
09:49:07.44 SWS - - - - Idling
09:49:07.58 LSH - - - - Idling
09:49:08.08 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:49:08.09 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:49:08.10 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:57:02.01 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:58:23.06 LSH - - - - Idling
09:58:23.42 SWS - - - - Idling
09:58:23.58 USH - - - - Idling
09:58:26.86 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:58:31.94 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:31.95 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:31.98 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:33.39 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:58:35.00 USH - - - - Idling
09:58:36.53 SWS - - - - Idling

```

09:58:36.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:58:36.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:58:39.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:58:41.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:58:42.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:58:46.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:58:46.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:58:46.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:58:51.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:58:52.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:12.65	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
09:59:12.66	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
09:59:15.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:17.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:20.27	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
09:59:20.28	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
09:59:22.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:26.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:29.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:30.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:33.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:59:34.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:37.03	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
09:59:37.04	USH	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
09:59:38.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:40.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:41.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:52.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 9 deg C
10:01:06.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:01:07.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:01:12.49	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:01:14.23	SWS	179.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:01:15.72	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:01:17.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:09:44.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:09:44.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:09:45.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:09:49.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:09:49.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:09:49.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:09:50.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:09:51.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:09:53.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:09:59.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:01.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:10:01.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:10:01.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:10:03.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:10:03.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:06.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:06.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:10:06.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:10:08.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:10.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:12.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:16.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:10:16.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:10:16.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:10:26.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:10:27.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:29.27	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
10:10:29.28	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
10:10:31.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:10:34.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:37.55	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
10:10:39.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:10:42.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:42.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:10:44.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

10:11:08.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:11:09.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:11:11.45	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:11:13.20	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:11:14.11	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:11:16.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:18.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:11:21.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:55.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:11:56.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:11:57.63	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:11:58.55	SWS	81.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:12:01.19	SWS	81.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:12:02.32	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:12:03.80	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:12:04.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:44.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:13:45.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:51.32	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:13:53.08	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:13:53.99	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:13:55.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:37.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:37.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:38.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:40.15	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:14:44.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:14:44.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:14:44.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:14:45.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:14:46.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:46.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:52.21	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:14:53.97	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:14:54.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:56.14	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:15:00.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:15:00.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:15:00.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:15:12.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:13.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:13.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:13.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:17:14.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:23.20	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:17:24.96	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:17:26.10	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:17:31.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:33.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:17:36.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:40.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:42.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:43.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:45.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:17:47.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:49.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:50.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:18:00.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:05.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:53.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:54.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:54.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:02.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:02.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:02.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:04.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:21:05.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:05.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:13.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:21:44.04	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
10:21:47.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:47.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:47.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:48.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:21:49.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:49.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:51.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:51.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:53.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:53.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:57.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:02.68	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:24:07.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:07.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:07.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:09.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:24:10.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:10.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:16.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:16.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:18.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:18.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:19.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:20.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:20.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:20.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:21.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:24:22.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:22.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:24.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:24.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:26.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:27.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:30.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:37.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 9 deg C
10:25:13.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:13.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:13.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:14.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:25:15.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:15.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:16.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:16.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:18.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:19.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:24.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:54.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:54.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:54.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:28.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:27:29.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:27:31.37	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:27:33.12	SWS	179.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:27:34.04	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:27:35.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:32.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:29:33.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:29:35.05	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:29:36.83	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:29:37.75	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:29:38.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:28.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:30:29.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:31.66	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:30:33.42	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:30:34.34	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:30:35.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:30.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

10:31:31.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:32.73	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:31:33.07	SWS	163.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:31:34.82	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:31:35.73	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:31:36.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:53.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:53.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:54.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:55.60	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:33:09.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:09.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:09.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:11.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:33:11.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:12.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:13.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:13.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:15.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:15.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:20.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:24.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:24.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:24.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:25.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:33:26.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:26.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:29.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:29.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:31.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:32.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:35.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:39.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:39.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:39.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:40.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:33:41.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:41.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:49.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:35:40.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:40.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:40.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:41.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:35:42.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:35:43.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:35:51.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:03.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:03.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:03.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:04.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:37:05.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:05.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:06.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:06.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:08.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:08.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:13.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:16.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:37:16.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:37:16.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:38:33.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:33.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:33.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:34.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:38:35.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:38:36.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:38:40.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:40.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:43.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

10:38:47.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:45.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:39:48.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:39:50.05	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:39:51.81	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:39:52.79	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:39:54.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:45.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:40:46.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:40:49.05	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:40:50.83	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:40:52.31	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:40:54.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:48.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:41:49.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:51.55	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:41:53.30	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:41:54.33	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:41:55.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:56.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:42:57.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:42:59.48	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:43:01.25	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:43:02.41	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:43:03.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:07.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:43:07.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:09.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:10.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:11.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:14.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:43:16.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:17.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:19.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:43:28.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:29.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:44:06.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:44:07.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:08.55	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:44:09.50	SWS	83.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:44:13.80	SWS	83.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:44:14.98	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:44:15.89	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:44:17.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:19.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:20.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:40.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:45:41.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:43.24	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:45:45.00	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:45:45.92	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:45:46.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:28.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:46:29.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:30.66	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:46:32.44	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:46:33.38	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:46:34.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:05.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:48:06.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:48:08.95	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:48:10.71	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:48:11.73	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:48:12.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:07.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:50:08.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:50:10.41	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:50:12.17	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:50:13.11	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000

10:50:14.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:27.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:51:27.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:51:28.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:51:30.46	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:51:34.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:34.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:34.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:35.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:51:37.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:51:37.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:51:38.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:38.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:40.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:51:41.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:51:45.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:30.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:30.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:30.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:32.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:58:33.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:33.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:38.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:58:38.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:58:41.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:49.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:01:17.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:17.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:18.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:19.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:01:19.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:01:19.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:01:22.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:23.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:24.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:01:25.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:01:29.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:03:25.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 9 geg C
11:04:32.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:32.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:33.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:35.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:35.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:35.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:36.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:04:37.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:37.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:45.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:30.51	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:05:32.27	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:05:33.22	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:05:49.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:49.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:49.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:50.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:05:51.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:51.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:59.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:01.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:01.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:01.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:03.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:06:04.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:04.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:07.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:07.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:09.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:09.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:12.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

11:06:35.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:35.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:35.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:08.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:08:09.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:10.79	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:08:11.74	SWS	89.4	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:08:12.09	SWS	125.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:08:13.12	SWS	125.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:08:15.22	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:08:16.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:12.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:10:13.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:15.11	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:10:16.88	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:10:17.80	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:10:18.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:20.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:11:21.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:23.69	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:11:25.48	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:11:26.40	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:11:27.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:29.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:12:30.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:12:32.18	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:12:33.96	SWS	0.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:12:34.88	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:12:35.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:36.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:13:37.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:13:39.53	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:13:41.32	SWS	179.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:13:42.25	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:13:43.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:06.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:07.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:07.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:09.03	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:15:12.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:12.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:12.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:14.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:15:15.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:15.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:16.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:16.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:18.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:19.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:24.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:24.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:15:24.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:15:24.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:15:40.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:40.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:40.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:16:00.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:16:01.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:16:07.12	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:16:08.92	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:16:11.57	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:16:12.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:36.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:17:37.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:39.97	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:17:41.72	SWS	179.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:17:42.65	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:17:43.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:13.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

11:18:13.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:18:14.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:45.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:19:45.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:19:45.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:19:47.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:19:47.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:48.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:50.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:19:50.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:19:52.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:52.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:56.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:00.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:00.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:00.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:02.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:21:02.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:03.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:11.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:45.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:45.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:45.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:46.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:21:47.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:47.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:55.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:00.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:00.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:00.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:50.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:50.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:51.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:52.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:52.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:22:53.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:54.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:54.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:56.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:57.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:57.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:59.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:23:01.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:01.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:23:01.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:03.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:23:04.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:23:05.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:05.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:05.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:06.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:23:07.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:23:08.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:23:15.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:23:18.83	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:23:20.59	SWS	0.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:23:22.19	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:24:21.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:24:22.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:24:22.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:23.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:25:24.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:26.57	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:25:28.34	SWS	179.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:25:29.49	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:25:30.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:31.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:27:32.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:34.46	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000

11:27:36.25	SWS	0.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:27:37.17	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:27:38.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:40.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:28:41.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:42.66	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:28:44.46	SWS	179.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:28:45.44	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:28:46.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:38.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:38.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:38.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:41.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:41.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:41.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:43.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:29:44.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:44.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:46.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:48.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:52.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:52.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:16.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:31:16.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:31:16.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:31:20.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:31:21.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:31:24.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:24.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:25.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:26.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:31:27.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:31:27.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:31:28.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:28.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:30.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:31:31.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:31:35.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:31:37.92	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:31:39.69	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:31:47.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:47.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:47.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:48.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:31:49.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:31:49.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:31:58.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:33:46.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:33:46.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:33:46.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:33:48.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:33:49.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:33:49.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:33:57.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:11.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:11.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:11.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:12.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:34:13.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:13.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:22.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:30.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:30.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:30.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:11.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:11.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:12.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:14.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:14.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:35:14.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:15.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:35:16.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:16.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:25.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:30.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:30.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:30.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:32.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:35:33.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:33.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:41.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:11.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:11.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:11.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:12.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:36:13.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:13.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:21.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:21.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:22.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:23.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:24.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:24.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:25.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:36:27.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:27.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:29.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:29.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:35.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:37:56.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:56.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:56.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:58.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:38:59.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:39:02.19	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:39:03.96	SWS	179.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:39:04.88	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:39:05.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:06.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:41:07.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:41:08.58	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:41:10.32	SWS	0.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:41:11.25	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:41:12.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:12.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:42:13.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:42:15.61	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:42:17.39	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:42:18.36	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:42:19.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:49.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:43:52.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:53.43	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:43:55.23	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:43:56.17	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:43:57.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:45:07.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** Frezer temp 8 deg C
11:46:50.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:46:51.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:46:53.26	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:46:55.05	SWS	179.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:46:55.64	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
11:46:56.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:55.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:55.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:56.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:57.39	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:48:00.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:48:00.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:48:01.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:48:02.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:48:03.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:48:03.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:48:03.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:48:05.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:48:06.76	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
11:48:07.94	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:48:08.86	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
11:48:11.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:48:14.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** endex

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	18/08/08	Flight	B400	log pages	3
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	CAVIAR			
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Exeter			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection							X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							X
FERA on			at time	05:30			
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	16.8°C	Ch	16.9°C	Ch18	16.2°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on			at time	05:33			
Initial target temperatures	Hot	288.4	Cold	285.4			
Target heating							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	05:37			
Scan indication		Monitor	>		Visual		X

Deimos

Deimos Orientation (Nadir or Zenith)							Z
Close all Deimos circuit breakers							X
Turn on Deimos CPU							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Start Deimos Software			at time	10:40			
Initial target temperatures	Hot	287.5	Cold	286.4			
Target heating							X
Scan indication		Monitor	>		Visual		X
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	07:19			
Brightness temps 'sensible'							X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.6	Cold	284.6		
	Deimos:	Hot	344.9	Cold	297.0		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B			
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)			
	54.4	14.9	54.7	13.2			
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20		
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)		
	39.17	32.81	40.29	41.43	43.03		

Power changeover

Headset on before start							
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.						
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)							
Exit Deimos Software (x)							
POWER CHANGEOVER							
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton						
Restart Deimos Software							
System running again						at time	

Flight #	B400	Date	18/08/08	Operator(s)	Pollard	log page	3	of	3
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	<i>Remarks</i>				Sys		

Data Processing Log		Initials	Date
Flight data copied from MARSS/Deimos PC flash disk to Martian C:\Bxxx\			
Check disc space on flash disk (need >~10 MB free)			
Copy* Martian logged data from to C:\Bxxx\			
Wave processing run and BT files generated			
DQM file generated and uploaded			
NetCDF file generated and uploaded			
C:\Bxxx\ copied to USB drive or CD			
Data processing issues/notes:			

CAVJAL.

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B400**.....

Date **18/09/28**.....

Operator's name: **S.P. OSBURN**.....

Page **1**..... of **2**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
0645								Pre-flight. Wet read zero good. Dry read zero poor on first attempt (all -ve). 2 nd attempt good.
0755								Labview - new software ("FIX. vi") Could not talk to dry read: had to change com port ^{name} on Labview prompt. Had to chiller off / no water yet.
0800	TRANSIT	FL110						Temp & RHs look OK. all RHs $\leq 30\%$. DEY!!
0818		FL200	~2.0			OFF		Pre-heater ON.
0848							set to 35°C	OFF to reset comms for chiller.
0845								Fill chiller with H ₂ O & switch on.
0849								Back on and recording - still no chiller.
0850								OFF again. slow to shut down Labview. Had to use task manager.
0857		FL255						Back on. Cannot talk to chiller. Did not try <u>all</u> comms settings, but a few random ones. Have unplugged serial link into hub.
0900		"					35°C	Use dry $\hat{=}$ $6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ (low) just above MBL??
0900							40°C	Set $\hat{=}$ profile descent into MBL!
		top of plume.						Use (0.53) upto $5.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^{-1}$.

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B400:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	I've just checked and it appears to have gone awol. I think you may as well upload without it as it isn't likely to turn up. Dr Phil Rosenberg
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
AMS / SP2 log	AMS / SP2 operator does not create a log sheet
TAFTS	TAFTS operator does not create a log sheet

AMS - not yet fitted Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	08 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following video recordings in avi format should be available at the BADC :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_080229_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_090229_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_100229_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_110229_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_120229_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_080223_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_090223_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_100223_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_110223_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_120223_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_080222_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_090222_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_100222_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_110222_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_120222_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_080226_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_090226_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_100226_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_110226_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080918_r0_b400_120226_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.